

Digital students go to campus: did stress and anxiety affect the intention for organization?

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ABSTRACT

The study delves into the behavioral shifts observed in "digital students" transitioning from distance to onsite learning during the Generation Z era, influenced significantly by the disruptive effects of the COVID-19 pandemic. Technological advancements have reshaped students' perspectives, rendering educational and organizational engagements more accessible via platforms like video conferencing. However, the return to onsite learning has prompted a notable culture shock, leading to heightened levels of stress and anxiety among digital students. This research aims to examine the psychological ramifications of stress and anxiety on post-pandemic student attitudes toward extracurricular organizational intention. Employing the depression anxiety stress scale (DASS-42) and conducting multiple linear regression analysis on a sample of 420 respondents, the study reveals a significant negative impact of stress level (-35.6%) on students' intentions to engage in organizational activities. Additionally, anxiety levels contribute to a variation of -6.8%. These findings underscore the intricate relationship between psychological factors and student participation, underscoring the imperative to address stress and anxiety to foster robust involvement in campus organizational endeavors.

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1. INTRODUCTION

According to [1], [2] the emergence of the digital student often referred to as the "brick and click" generation, has brought about a significant shift in the education landscape, especially during the pandemic era. This generation encompasses students who have been exposed to online or hybrid learning methods. This transformation has been particularly pronounced in the context of Generation Z, encompassing individuals born between 1998 and 2023 [3].

The entire learning process, educational interactions, counseling, and guidance from lecturers or professors are now conducted exclusively from the students' own residences, connected to the internet [3], [4]. The digital students of this Z generation, immersed in online learning, have adapted to a flexible learning environment with minimal effort, striving for academic excellence or active participation in various organizational activities that simply through a screen [5], [6]. This shift in learning patterns has generated a significant impact on the habits and attitudes of students toward the educational and organizational extracurricular cycle [7].

Research by Ilduganova *et al.* [8] in Utama and Sunu [9] states, that psychological issues related to online learning have become increasingly prevalent during the pandemic, affecting the mental health and well-being of both students and educators. The transition to online schooling, exacerbated by the COVID-19

epidemic, has presented a multitude of psychological challenges [10], [11]. However, in the post-pandemic era, these concerns have somewhat dissipated as educational activities returned to a "hybrid" model, combining both onsite and online components [12]. Despite the hybrid model being a viable solution, the online learning habits acquired during the pandemic persist, posing a potential threat that is often overlooked by various stakeholders, particularly parents [13], [14].

Research by Ayasrah *et al.* [15] describes the attitude and tendency, that gives rise to a shift in the habitual patterns experienced by both school and university students in relation to teaching and learning activities, even education itself. According to [16] and [17], psychological issues associated with online learning have become increasingly prevalent during the pandemic, with students and educators encountering various obstacles that may impact their mental health and overall well-being.

The transition to online schooling, exacerbated by the COVID-19 epidemic, has led to several psychological challenges [18]. However, in the post-pandemic era, all these anxieties instantly dissipate as everything returns to a new normal, and the entire campus activities undergo a transformation into an onsite (some of them are hybrid) that amalgamates both onsite and online activities [19], [20]. Despite the effectiveness of the hybrid transformation in this scenario, the online learning habits persist in the students, thus being perceived as a potential threat or something that cannot be accepted simultaneously [21], [22].

According to the research conducted by Aristika *et al.* [20], as outlined in [23], these disparities and negative stigmas elicit various responses felt by university students, particularly in their intent to participate in extracurricular organizational activities or student associations. A tendency arises for a sense of concern, such as the apprehension associated with the necessity of learning in a school or campus setting [24]. The perspective of digital students as representatives of Generation Z, who exclusively experience online learning, often leads to feelings of insecurity due to their perceived lack of proficiency and familiarity with effective learning and organizational activities [20].

The research by Yang *et al.* [25] states, that the competency level expected in higher education institutions extends beyond academic proficiency; it also encompasses the development of soft skills, including leadership, teamwork, and communication [26]. Consequently, a majority of students may exhibit a lack of engagement, resulting in a detrimental impact on their personal and professional development [27]. Research suggests that the deficiency in students' inclination to engage in organizational activities is often attributed to two factors, namely, anxiety, and stress levels experienced by students [20]. Anxiety and stress represent prevalent mental health concerns among students pursuing higher education [28], [29].

These issues can significantly impact students' academic performance, social relationships, and overall well-being in organizational activity [28]. Therefore, it is essential to understand how anxiety and stress levels can influence students' refusal intention to join organizations in higher education [30]. Understanding the implications of stress and anxiety on students' inclination to participate in campus organizations, is crucial in the post-pandemic era [30]. The depression anxiety stress scale (DASS-42) serves as a valuable instrument for gauging and quantifying these psychological factors. This self-report questionnaire is designed to provide a comprehensive assessment of the severity of symptoms related to depression, anxiety, and stress, offering insights into the multifaceted aspects of mental health [28], [31].

In the aftermath of the pandemic, according to [32], the pervasive effects of anxiety and stress continue to exert a significant influence on students' decisions regarding engagement in campus organizations with approximately 80.2% of students, and the majority of them are university students consisting of 46.3%. Elevated stress levels may contribute to a heightened sense of reluctance among students, deterring them from actively participating in extracurricular activities [33]. The fear of academic burdens, coupled with concerns about time management and the ability to balance organizational commitments with academic responsibilities, can amplify stress levels among students [34]–[36].

Moreover, anxiety stemming from the uncertainties of the post-pandemic landscape may instigate a sense of apprehension among students [21], [30]. The challenges associated with adapting to new hybrid learning models, coupled with concerns about health and safety, further exacerbate anxiety levels [37]. This heightened state of anxiety may manifest as a reluctance to commit to campus organizations, as students grapple with the need to prioritize their mental well-being and academic pursuits [38], [39].

The refusal intention of students to engage in campus organizations can also be linked to the social and interpersonal dynamics influenced by stress and anxiety [40], [41]. Students experiencing heightened stress levels may find it challenging to navigate social interactions, contributing to a reluctance to join groups or participate in collaborative activities [41]. The fear of judgment or the perception of inadequate social skills may act as deterrents, hindering students from fully immersing themselves in the vibrant social fabric of campus life [42].

This research employs the DASS-42, a well-established psychometric instrument specifically designed to measure the severity of symptoms related to depression, anxiety, and stress [43]. The utilization of the DASS-42 in this context is crucial as it provides a nuanced and comprehensive assessment of the psychological dimensions pertinent to stress and anxiety, allowing for a more granular understanding of their impact [44]. The

DASS-42 is particularly advantageous due to its modification, which tailors the instrument to the specific nuances of the academic environment and the organizational context under investigation [43]. This modification ensures that the questionnaire remains contextually relevant, capturing stressors and anxiety triggers that are pertinent to the academic and organizational challenges faced by college students [44]. By incorporating these adjustments, the research aims to enhance the validity and reliability of the instrument, ensuring that it effectively measures the variables of interest within the study's framework [41], [44].

To collect and analyze data, this research uses an item response theory (IRT) approach based on a survey constructed using DASS-42, which is aimed at new university students who have recently experienced onsite learning [44]. Meanwhile, to calculate the level of influence mathematically, multiple linear regression was used to determine the relationship between stress, anxiety, and organizational intentions of 'digital students'. anxiety [40], [41]. The coefficients from the regression results aim to show the relationship between variables, indicating that increased levels of stress or anxiety are associated with a higher likelihood of reluctance to engage in organizational activities. In contrast, a negative coefficient indicates a negative relationship, indicating that higher levels of stress or anxiety are associated with a reduced tendency to reject organizational participation.

2. METHOD

The research methodology selected emphasizes the pivotal role of gathering numerical data and employing statistical methods to substantiate the identified impacts. Utilizing IBM SPSS 23, a renowned statistical software package, the statistical computations were conducted, leveraging its comprehensive capabilities recognized within the research community as the "statistical package for the social sciences." To evaluate the influence of stress and anxiety as variables on students' intentions, a rigorous multiple linear regression analysis was conducted [45]. Adopting a quantitative-confirmatory approach in psychometric research, the study delves into the ramifications of stress (X1) and anxiety levels (X2) on students' inclination to engage in organizational activities (Y) amidst the post-pandemic landscape. The conceptual model elucidating these relationships is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Research model of stress and anxiety level affect organizational intention

This statistical technique, as introduced and practiced by [46], allows us to determine the percentage and direction of the impact of independent variables on the dependent variable, resulting in a coefficient derived from a linear equation. There are several steps that need to be taken in analyzing psychometric data using multiple linear regression according to [46], which the first step is to determine the distribution of the data, as well as the mean and standard deviation of the test population.

Next, a normality test is performed to determine if the data follows a normal distribution. An ANOVA (F-test) is then conducted to determine if there are significant differences between groups. Multicollinearity is also checked to ensure that there is no high correlation between independent variables. A T-test is performed to compare the means of two groups between the independent variables (stress and anxiety levels) toward the dependent variable (student intention). Model analysis regression is then conducted to determine the relationship between the dependent and independent variables. Finally, the DASS-42 result is used to measure anxiety and stress scaling.

According to [46]–[48] the minimum required sample size should be at least 10 times the number of questionnaire items or constructs of the variables under investigation. Based on the results of the modified and adapted DASS-42 questionnaires, a total of 42 questionnaire items necessitating a minimum sample size of 420 respondents to be considered ideal for testing. In the initial selection, 442 respondents returned to the survey, however, due to saturation, the sample was reevaluated and refined until ultimately only 420 were accepted as active students from various universities in Bandung, including two private universities and a technological institute. Secondary data was gathered through a literature review, while the remaining data collected underwent analysis through a multiple linear regression test, as presented in (1).

$$Y = a + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \dots + \beta_n x_n + e \quad (1)$$

Notes:

- Y : Student intention to join the organization
- A : Constanta
- β_1 : Coefficient variable of stress level
- β_2 : Coefficient variable of anxiety level
- x_1 : Independent variable of stress
- x_2 : Independent variable of anxiety
- E : Error (variable of another effect beyond the model)

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study involved a robust sample size comprising 420 students meticulously drawn from three esteemed private campuses in Bandung. Among these respondents, females constituted 50.48% ($n = 212$), while males accounted for 49.62% ($n = 208$), ensuring a balanced representation across gender lines. The research endeavors encompassed a multifaceted array of statistical analyses, meticulously designed to provide a comprehensive understanding of the intricate dynamics at play.

Embarking upon the descriptive analysis, the dataset derived from all 420 completed surveys underwent meticulous examination. The calculated mean values for each variable unveiled essential insights into the psychological landscape of the respondents. Notably, the mean stress level was identified at 23.1, indicating a moderate level of perceived stress among the student population. Similarly, the mean anxiety level was determined to be 15.6, suggestive of a discernible degree of apprehension and worry prevalent within the sampled cohort. Furthermore, the mean value of 31 for Student's Intention underscored a reasonably positive disposition toward organizational involvement among the student body.

Complementing the mean values, the standard deviation values provided crucial insights into the dispersion of data around the mean, elucidating the variability within the sampled population. With a standard deviation of 8.8 for stress level, 8.1 for anxiety level, and 9.4 for student intention, it became apparent that while there existed a degree of uniformity in stress and anxiety levels, the intention towards organizational engagement exhibited relatively higher variability among respondents. All the data of descriptive statistics can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics

Parameter(s)	Stress level	Anxiety level	Student' intention
N	420	420	420
Mean	23.1	15.6	31
Median (Q2)	18.0	12.0	26.0
Std. deviation	8.781 (8.8)	8.122 (8.1)	9.397 (9.4)
Min	7	9	23
Max	36	28	42

In this research, we undertook a classical assumption test aimed at determining the normality of the data under scrutiny. Our objective was to ascertain whether the dataset conforms to a normal distribution pattern. To accomplish this, the residual Q-Q plot graph was employed which was generated utilizing the SPSS 23 application. The Q-Q plot is a graphical tool commonly utilized in statistical analysis to assess the normality assumption by comparing the quantiles of the data distribution against those of a theoretical normal distribution to analyze the distribution of residue [46].

Figure 2 illustrates the graphical representation of the analysis, showcasing the alignment or deviation of the data points from the diagonal line, which represents acceptance of normality. The results of the visual analysis on the Q-Q plot graph show that the distribution of residues is normally distributed with a bimodal shape. According to [1], [46], [47], the determination test is carried out to determine the degree to which the factors between the independent variables influence the dependent variable. In this research, the R and R square values were obtained from the two independent variables including; levels of stress (X1) and anxiety (X2) on students' intention (Y)

Figure 2. Q-Q plot normality test result

Based on Table 2, it can be explained the regression analysis conducted on the model reveals a moderate negative correlation ($R = -0.437$) between the dependent and independent variables. Furthermore, the coefficient of determination (R square) indicates that approximately 37.3% of the variability in the dependent variable is explained by the independent variables in the model. The standard error of the estimate (Std error) is relatively low at 9.826, signifying the model is a good fit for the observed data. Importantly, the statistical significance (Sig.) of 0.000 implies that the observed relationship is highly unlikely to have occurred by chance, reinforcing the robustness of the findings. Additionally, the Durbin-Watson statistic of 2.226 suggests no significant autocorrelation issues in the residuals, affirming the independence of consecutive observations in the regression model. Overall, these statistics collectively contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the model's effectiveness and the strength of the relationships it captures [49].

Table 2. Determination (R square) test result

Model	R	R square	Std error	Sig.	Durbin-Watson
Determination	-0.437	0.373	9.826	0.000	2.226

After the R square has been identified, ANOVA known as Variance analysis is done to examine mean differences between groups of data or populations [50], [51]. It is employed in statistical measurements to divide the total variance found in the data into two parts: systematic components and random variables. Random factors have no statistical impact on the provided data set, but systematic factors have an impact on each variable, causing a difference or influence. The ANOVA was employed in the data analysis to identify the influence of the independent factors on the research-dependent variable [50], [52].

As shown in Table 3, related to ANOVA (F-test), it is described that the calculated F value obtained from the SPSS 23 application is 73.972 which is greater than 3.33, with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$, which clarifies that the regression model is acceptable and able to predict the relationship between the independent variable (stress and anxiety level) with the dependent variable (student' intention). Literally, after the variance test has been completed, a classic assumption must be made by estimating the variance inflation factor, or VIF, in regression analysis.

Table 3. ANOVA (F-test) result

Model	Df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Regression	2	649.8	73.972	0.000
Residual	41	67.85		
Total	47			

According to the research conducted by [46], the classic assumption test is a statistical criterion that must be fulfilled in an ordinary least-squares (OLS), as part of multiple linear regression. In normal cases, classic assumption tests must be performed to confirm that the resulting regression model is the optimal model in terms of estimating accuracy, lack of bias, and consistency. In this research, there are four parts of classic assumption have been done, which are; i) normality test (Q-Q plot) can be seen in Figure 2, ii) multicollinearity test, iii) heteroscedasticity test, and iv) autocorrelation test [53]. According to [46], [53], the multicollinearity test was done as part of the multiple regression analysis to ascertain the presence of interrelationships among the independent and dependent variables. Such interrelationships could potentially introduce bias into the statistical results.

The primary objective of this analysis was to investigate whether the explanatory variables exhibited substantial associations that might compromise the reliability and validity of the statistical findings. Multicollinearity, if detected, can pose challenges in disentangling the unique contributions of each independent variable [54]. Consequently, it becomes imperative to not only identify but also address these interactions to ensure the accuracy and dependability of the statistical analysis. For this research, the multicollinearity of all variables can be seen in Table 4.

Table 4. Multicollinearity test result

No.	Eigenvalue	Condition index	Constant	Stress level	Anxiety level	Collinearity value	
						Tolerance	VIF
1	2.975	1.000	0.00	0.00	0.00	-	-
2	0.015	13.897	.61	0.17	0.16	0.563	1.778
3	0.009	17.847	.39	0.82	0.84	0.563	1.778

As depicted in Table 4, the VIF for both predictors X1 and X2 stands at 1.788, significantly lower than the commonly accepted threshold of 10. Additionally, the condition index values for X1 and X2 are computed to be 13.897 and 17.847, respectively, both well below the conventional cutoff of 30. These results unequivocally indicate the absence of multicollinearity issues among the variables examined in this study. Therefore, it can be deduced that there is no compelling evidence to suggest multicollinearity among the predictors, ensuring the reliability of the regression analysis conducted.

To ascertain the presence of heteroscedasticity, scatterplots serve as a crucial tool to scrutinize the dispersion of data across independent variables concerning the dependent variable [55]. Examining the distribution, it becomes evident that the data does not exhibit a centralized pattern and extends extensively from top to bottom. This absence of a discernible pattern indicates the absence of heteroscedasticity, as depicted in Figure 3. Consequently, the data successfully satisfies the conventional assumption test, reaffirming its suitability for further investigation via the linear regression test.

Figure 3. Scatterplot of Heteroscedasticity

Turner [55] states that the autocorrelation test (Durbin Watson) is used to determine whether there is a correlation between a test period and the pre-test period (t-1). In summary, autocorrelation seeks to determine the effect of independent variables (X1 and X2) on the dependent variable (Y), and hence there must be no connection observed between the present data and past observational data which the result of the autocorrelation test can be seen in Table 5.

Table 5. Durbin-Watson test result

Population	A	Threshold (dU)	Durbin-Watson (d)	Max DW (4-du)
420	5%	1.758	2.226	2.242

Based on the results of statistical calculations related to autocorrelation using Durbin-Watson, a value of 1.758 was obtained for dU taken from a population of 420 ($N = 420$), while the Durbin-Watson based on SPSS calculation results was 2.226. There is no autocorrelation in this research data because the position of the Durbin-Watson measurement results is exactly between the lower threshold and the maximum DW ($dU < d < 4 - dU$) which can be written in the mathematical form $1.758 < 2.226 < 2.242$.

In multiple linear regression, the T-test is used to examine the level of truth and validity of the values of confirmatory quantitative research data and hypotheses [46]. In this case, no significant differences were found regarding the mean of the sample size measured on two independent variables, including stress and anxiety levels on students' intentions to join organizations or extracurriculars on campus. The results of the T-test can be seen in Table 6.

Table 6. T-test result

Independent variable	Std. error	Significance
Constant	3.236	0.000
Stress level (X1)	0.084	0.002
Anxiety level (X2)	0.079	0.000

Based on the results of the T-test which focuses on significance values, it was found that the stress level (X1) variable had a significant value of 0.002, where this value was smaller than 0.05, thus indicating that this independent variable directly influenced student intention to attend the organization as the dependent variable. Likewise, another independent variable, namely anxiety level (X2) has a significance value of 0.000, which is also smaller than 0.05, so it can be concluded that these two independent variables influence digital students' intentions to join organizations in the post-pandemic.

According to [46], [53], the process of multiple linear regression analysis was undertaken to ascertain the extent of influence exerted by independent variables on the dependent variable. In this context, the multiple linear regression analysis was conducted utilizing the SPSS 24 application. The findings revealed a negative influence between the variables stress and anxiety level on students' intention to engage in organizational activities, as indicated in Table 7. This statistical procedure was employed to explore and quantify the relationship between the specified independent and dependent variables.

Table 7. Regression model analysis

Predictor	Estimate (β)	Standard error	T-Value	Probability (p)
Constant	28.683	3.236	8.865	0.000
Stress level	-.356	.084	3.214	0.001
Anxiety level	-.068	.079	1.710	0.000

Based on the data processing results for multiple linear regression analysis using regression analysis modeling, the computed values were obtained as depicted in Table 7. Specifically, the calculated T-value for the variable stress level was found to be 3.214, indicating a negative impact of stress levels on students' intention to actively engage in organizational activities in the post-pandemic period. Concurrently, for the variable anxiety level, the computed t-value was 1.710, providing evidence of a negative influence of anxiety on students' intention to actively participate in organizational activities during the post-pandemic era. When translated into a mathematical form of a multiple linear regression model, the obtained regression equation

aligns with (2). These statistical outcomes contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the quantitative relationships between the identified variables.

$$Y = 28.683 - 0.356 x_1 - 0.058 x_2 + e \tag{2}$$

The (2) provides a descriptive relationship between the independent variables and the student intention to participate in organizations in the post-pandemic era. In the absence of any external influences from other variables, the baseline value for the dependent variable is ascertained at 28.683. This fundamental value signifies the anticipated Student Intention in the absence of any additional factors. However, as the model accounts for the impact of the stress level variable (X1), an intriguing pattern emerges. For every unit increase in the stress level, there is a corresponding decrease in student intention by -0.356. This suggests that heightened stress levels exert a negative influence on the inclination of students to engage in organizational activities, indicating a potential deterrent effect.

Likewise, the model incorporates an examination of the influence of the anxiety level variable (X2) on student intention. It reveals that for every unit increase in anxiety level, there is a corresponding decrease of -0.068 in student intention (Y). This implies that increasing levels of anxiety contribute to a diminishing inclination among students to participate in campus organizations, underscoring the significance of addressing mental health concerns in fostering student engagement.

The presence of the symbol “+e” in the regression model introduces the acknowledgment of potential external factors or errors that are not accounted for in the measured variables. This signifies the complexity of real-world scenarios, where factors beyond the scope of the study may influence Student Intention. After carrying out the results of multiple linear regression calculations, the influence of stress and anxiety levels on students' intentions to join the organization was then analyzed using DASS-42, which was originally conceptualized by Crawford and Henry [56] and further developed by Widyana *et al* [57]. For the purpose of this research, the researcher utilized the DASS-42 literature by Hsia *et al.* [58], with adjustments as outlined in Table 8.

Table 8. Stress level classification (DASS-42)

Classification	Interval score	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Normal	$x \leq 14$	112	29
Mild	$15 \leq x \leq 20$	199	47
Moderate	$21 \leq x \leq 33$	91	22
Severe	$x > 33$	8	2
Total (N)		420	100

Analysis result from Table 8, reveals that the majority of "digital students" who have recently experienced onsite learning report experiencing mild levels of stress, comprising 199 individuals (47%). Following this group, there are 112 students (29%) who perceive their stress levels as normal or non-existent. More intense stress levels, 91 individuals (22%) express experiencing moderate stress, often characterized by observable changes in behavior such as quick irritability and restlessness. Notably, a smaller group of 8 individuals (2%) is identified as facing severe stress, marked by tendencies towards difficulty in relaxation and prolonged episodes of anger. Apart from stress, there are analysis results regarding the average level of anxiety experienced by the new student population using the DASS-42 as can be seen in Table 9.

Table 9. Anxiety level classification (DASS-42)

Classification	Interval score	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Normal	$x \leq 10$	226	54
Mild	$11 \leq x \leq 16$	143	34
Moderate	$17 \leq x \leq 21$	40	10
Severe	$x > 22$	11	3
Total (N)		420	100

Based on the results of the analysis and classification of anxiety levels derived from questionnaires administered to students of higher education institutions in the city of Bandung, a total of 226 respondents were identified. These respondents were categorized as having normal anxiety conditions, constituting the majority of the population at a percentage of 54%. Subsequently, 143 respondents were classified as having low anxiety levels (mild) at a percentage of 34%, characterized by occasional worry under specific circumstances. There are two hypotheses that can be concluded in this research, respectively: H1: stress level has an impact on student intention.

In multiple linear regression, the T-values from prior statistical tests are utilized. Hypothesis 1 (H1) concerning the influence of stress level (X1) on students' intention to participate in extracurricular campus organizations (Y) is substantiated based on the T-value analysis presented in Table 6. The calculated T-value (t-count) surpasses the critical T-value (t-table), expressed mathematically as $t\text{-count} > t\text{-table}$ ($3.214 > 1.645$). Consequently, from the hypothesis testing analysis, it is inferred that the alternative hypothesis (H1) is accepted.

The percentage of the impact is negative, denoted as -0.356 or -35.6%, emphasizing the adverse influence of stress levels on students' intention to engage in organizational extracurricular activities. Thus, it can be interpreted that the higher the level of stress (X1) experienced by students, the lower their intention to take part in organizational activities on campus (Y). These results are also in line with the research of [19], [44], that describes how stress can influence students' participation in organization activities by showing that stress has a significant negative impact on their participation intentions. Furthermore, in the other independent variable, namely the level of anxiety (X2), there is an alternative hypothesis (H2) which is symbolized as follows: H2: anxiety level has an impact on student intention.

The results of hypothesis testing for H2, examining the relationship between anxiety level (X2) and students' intention to engage in organizational activities (Y) within the campus environment, yield significant findings. The T-value analysis from Table 6 indicates that the calculated T-value (t-count) exceeds the critical T-value (t-table), specifically $t\text{-count} > t\text{-table}$ ($1.710 > 1.645$). Consequently, based on the hypothesis testing analysis, it is concluded that the alternative hypothesis (H2) is accepted. The percentage of the impact is negative, denoted as -0.068. This result suggests that the level of anxiety (X2) significantly influences students' intention to participate in campus organizational activities, with an impact percentage of 6.8%. The identified influence of anxiety is negative, quantified at -0.068. In other words, as the level of anxiety (X2) experienced by students increases, their intention to participate in campus organizational activities (Y) decreases.

The Impact of Stress on student intention to participate in an organization employing T-values from statistical tests, regarding the influence of stress level (X1) on students' intention to participate in organizational activities (Y) is supported. Based on the multiple regression analysis of T-value (T-count) clearly surpasses the critical T-value (t-table), indicating a substantial impact between the stress level on organizational intention. In simpler meaning, higher stress levels (X1) correspond to a significantly lower intention among students to engage in campus activities (Y). This research confirms aligned with the previous studies by [19], [43], [59], highlighting stress's profound negative impact on students' intention to participate in any organization.

On the other hand, for hypothesis 2 (H2), the impact of anxiety on student intention turning to anxiety (X2), hypothesis 2 (H2) is substantiated by the T-value analysis, indicating a substantial negative impact on student's intention to engage in campus organizational activities. The calculated T-value (T-count) clearly exceeds the critical T-value (T-table), leading to the acceptance of the alternative hypothesis (H2). The negative impact of anxiety is described as notable, indicating that as anxiety levels (X2) increase, students' intention to participate in campus activities (Y) notably decreases. This underscores the significant detrimental effect of anxiety on students' organizational participation intentions.

The subsequent focus shifts to a descriptive examination of stress and anxiety levels among students. In the context of moderate anxiety, a noteworthy proportion of respondents exhibited recurring anxiety symptoms, while severe anxiety, accounting for a considerable percentage, manifested in more urgent symptoms. This descriptive analysis provides a comprehensive overview of anxiety prevalence and severity among the sampled student population, building on the statistically significant evidence of stress and anxiety's impact on students' intentions to actively participate in organizational activities post-pandemic.

4. CONCLUSION

This research investigation examines the influence of stress and anxiety levels on students' intention to participate in campus extracurricular organizational activities in the post-pandemic era, with a focus on digital students who have recently experienced onsite or hybrid learning in Bandung City. The research findings that stress and anxiety levels have a detrimental influence on students' intention to engage and register as members of organizational extracurriculars, which is caused by the load of study or academic burden, fear of failure, and a lack of communication skills. To enhance student involvement in organizational extracurricular activities, research highlights the need to detect and resolve mental health concerns such as stress and anxiety. Seeking educational therapy or counseling, practicing self-care, and establishing boundaries are all methods to cope with post-pandemic stress.

The implications drawn from this research have great potential for developing targeted interventions and programs to improve the overall well-being of digital students, especially their intention to actively

participate in organizations. By addressing the stress and anxiety factors identified as independent variables, this intervention can increase student participation in organizational extracurricular activities and encourage them to return to being active in the onsite learning program.

Additionally, there is an urgent need for additional research to delve deeper into the complex relationships between stress, anxiety, and organizational activity. A suggestion for further research is the inclusion of online learning as an independent variable, mediating stress and anxiety in influencing students' intentions toward involvement in extracurricular organizations. These different approaches can yield valuable insights into the multifaceted dynamics of behavior.

To increase the accuracy of future investigations, researchers advise increasing the sample size to 500 respondents or above. This expanded sample will facilitate a more comprehensive exploration of the factors influencing intentions. It is necessary to explore further whether gender, parental background, and heredity can influence the results of the influence of stress and anxiety levels on intentions to participate in organizational activities.

In addition, the recommendation to use concrete psychometric analyses and sophisticated statistical methodologies, such as structural equation modeling (SEM), is also emphasized, especially when dealing with complex independent variables. This analytical approach will contribute to a more nuanced understanding of the complex interactions between various factors that influence students' intentions and behavior in organizational extracurricular activities.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. Zhang and X. Li, "COVID-19 Influenced survey on students' satisfaction with psychological acceptance based on the organization of online teaching and learning in English," *Frontiers in Psychology*, vol. 13, Jul. 2022, doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2022.940527.
- [2] T. Yuliantini *et al.*, "Online-learning program to develop leadership on student council organisation," *ICCD*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 303–307, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.33068/iccd.Vol3.Iss1.366.
- [3] O. Farrell and J. Brunton, "A balancing act: a window into online student engagement experiences," *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, vol. 17, no. 1, p. 25, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1186/s41239-020-00199-x.
- [4] H. Panduwiyasa, "The influence of knowledge management and Islamic leadership on organizational decision making for middle school muslim youth development," *Jurnal Tarbiyatuna*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 145–162, 2022, doi: <https://doi.org/10.31603/tarbiyatuna.v13i2.6652>.
- [5] A. W. Cole, L. Lennon, and N. L. Weber, "Student perceptions of online active learning practices and online learning climate predict online course engagement," *Interactive Learning Environments*, vol. 29, no. 5, pp. 866–880, Jul. 2021, doi: 10.1080/10494820.2019.1619593.
- [6] O. Rotar, "Online student support: a framework for embedding support interventions into the online learning cycle," *Research and Practice in Technology Enhanced Learning*, vol. 17, no. 1, p. 2, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.1186/s41039-021-00178-4.
- [7] P. C. Holzweiss, D. W. Walker, R. Chisum, and T. Sosebee, "Crisis planning for online students: lessons learned from a major disruption," *Online Learning*, vol. 24, no. 2, Jun. 2020, doi: 10.24059/olj.v24i2.2135.
- [8] G. M. Ilduganova, N. V. Tikhonova, and R. I. Galimullina, "Online learning issues in Russian universities," *Revista on line de Política e Gestão Educacional*, pp. 516–527, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.22633/rpge.v25iesp.1.14988.
- [9] G. A. Utama and I. G. K. A. Sunu, "School principal role in handling online learning issues during covid-19 pandemic," *International Journal of Educational Management and Innovation*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 183–197, May 2022, doi: 10.12928/ijemi.v3i2.5790.
- [10] S. N. Mousavizadeh, P. G. Merdasi, and M. Safari, "Psychological challenges of nurses in pandemic covid-19," *Psychology and Education Journal*, vol. 57, no. 9, pp. 6696–6709, 2020, doi: <https://doi.org/10.17762/pae.v57i9.3644>.
- [11] H. Panduwiyasa, H. C. Fikri, M. Saputra, and W. Puspitasari, "Sales system and pandemic: integrated ERP system design in sales for SME," in *2021 2nd international conference on information technology, advanced mechanical and electrical engineering (icitamee)*, 2022, p. 050004. doi: 10.1063/5.0104934.
- [12] N. Aisha and A. Ratra, "Online education amid COVID-19 pandemic and its opportunities, challenges and psychological impacts among students and teachers: a systematic review," *Asian Association of Open Universities Journal*, vol. 17, no. 3, pp. 242–260, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.1108/AAOUJ-03-2022-0028.
- [13] N. Osman, S. S. Mohd Noor, and N. C. Hat, "Online learning: student psychological challenges during a pandemic covid-19," *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, vol. 12, no. 1, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.6007/IJARBS/v12-i1/11636.
- [14] P. Ramadhanti, T. Y. Afandi, and E. W. Prastyaningtyas, "The effect of student activity in organizations on learning achievement and soft skill improvement," *International Journal of Research and Review*, vol. 8, no. 8, pp. 488–495, Aug. 2021, doi: 10.52403/ijrr.20210866.
- [15] S. Ayasrah, M. S. Alnasraween, A. Alshorman, and A. Aljarrah, "Attitudes of teachers and outstanding students towards blended learning in light of the Covid-19 pandemic in Jordan," *Pegem Journal of Education and Instruction*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 249–255, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.47750/pegegog.12.01.26.
- [16] X. Dong *et al.*, "A bibliometric analysis on global psychological and behavioral research landscape on covid-19 pandemic," *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, vol. 19, no. 2, p. 879, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.3390/ijerph19020879.
- [17] M. G. Maru, C. C. Pikirang, S. Setiawan, E. Z. O. Oroh, and N. Pelenkahu, "The internet use for autonomous learning during covid-19 pandemic and its hindrances," *International Journal of Interactive Mobile Technologies (IJIM)*, vol. 15, no. 18, p. 65, Sep. 2021, doi: 10.3991/ijim.v15i18.24553.
- [18] R. K. Dwivedi, M. Pandey, A. Vashisht, D. K. Pandey, and D. Kumar, "Assessing behavioral intention toward green hotels during COVID-19 pandemic: the moderating role of environmental concern," *Journal of Tourism Futures*, Feb. 2022, doi: 10.1108/JTF-05-2021-0116.

- [19] H. H. Alsowat, "Hybrid learning or virtual learning? effects on students' essay writing and digital literacy," *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 872–883, Jul. 2022, doi: 10.17507/jltr.1304.20.
- [20] A. Aristika, Darhim, D. Juandi, and Kusnandi, "The effectiveness of hybrid learning in improving of teacher-student relationship in terms of learning motivation," *Emerging Science Journal*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 443–456, Aug. 2021, doi: 10.28991/esj-2021-01288.
- [21] A. Raes, "Exploring student and teacher experiences in hybrid learning environments: does presence matter?," *Postdigital Science and Education*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 138–159, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.1007/s42438-021-00274-0.
- [22] H. Panduwiyasa, L. Andrawina, and I. K. Sriwana, "Modelling the adoption of open-source enterprise resource planning system in culinary SMEs," in *2022 3rd international conference on information technology and advanced mechanical and electrical engineering (icitamee)*, 2023, p. 050008. doi: 10.1063/5.0182714.
- [23] M. Li, "Learning behaviors and cognitive participation in online-offline hybrid learning environment," *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (iJET)*, vol. 17, no. 01, pp. 146–159, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.3991/ijet.v17i01.28715.
- [24] Q. Li, Z. Li, and J. Han, "A hybrid learning pedagogy for surmounting the challenges of the COVID-19 pandemic in the performing arts education," *Education and Information Technologies*, vol. 26, no. 6, pp. 7635–7655, Nov. 2021, doi: 10.1007/s10639-021-10612-1.
- [25] M. Yang, Q. Qu, Y. Shen, Z. Zhao, X. Chen, and C. Li, "An effective hybrid learning model for real-time event summarization," *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems*, vol. 32, no. 10, pp. 4419–4431, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.1109/TNNLS.2020.3017747.
- [26] R. Indra, M. Kustati, A. Saregar, W. Warnis, N. Nelmawarni, and Y. Qismullah, "The effect of principals' leadership towards effective learning at an Indonesian secondary school," *European Journal of Educational Research*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 1063–1074, Jul. 2020, doi: 10.12973/eu-jer.9.3.1063.
- [27] A. S. A. Ghani, A. F. A. Rahim, M. S. B. Yusoff, and S. N. H. Hadie, "Effective learning behavior in problem-based learning: a scoping review," *Medical Science Educator*, vol. 31, no. 3, pp. 1199–1211, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.1007/s40670-021-01292-0.
- [28] T. Alshammari, S. Alseraye, R. Alqasim, A. Rogowska, N. Alrasheed, and M. Alshammari, "Examining anxiety and stress regarding virtual learning in colleges of health sciences: a cross-sectional study in the era of the COVID-19 pandemic in Saudi Arabia," *Saudi Pharmaceutical Journal*, vol. 30, no. 3, pp. 256–264, Mar. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.jsps.2022.01.010.
- [29] T. Xu and H. Wang, "High prevalence of anxiety, depression, and stress among remote learning students during the COVID-19 pandemic: Evidence from a meta-analysis," *Frontiers in Psychology*, vol. 13, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2022.1103925.
- [30] M. Fawaz and A. Samaha, "E-learning: depression, anxiety, and stress symptomatology among Lebanese university students during COVID-19 quarantine," *Nursing Forum*, vol. 56, no. 1, pp. 52–57, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.1111/nuf.12521.
- [31] H. A. Maulana, "The influence of psychological impact of online learning during covid-19 on student's academic achievement: a case study at vocational higher education," *Psychocentrum Review*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 10–21, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.26539/pcr.31560.
- [32] H. A. Maulana, "Psychological impact of online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic: a case study on vocational higher education," *Indonesian Journal of Learning Education and Counseling*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 130–139, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.31960/ijolec.v3i2.833.
- [33] E. Schwaiger, S. S. Zehra, and I. Suneel, "Attachment, religiosity, and perceived stress among religious minorities during the covid-19 pandemic: the impact of cultural context," *Journal of Psychology and Theology*, vol. 50, no. 3, pp. 369–383, Sep. 2022, doi: 10.1177/00916471211025532.
- [34] S. A. Smith, S. R. Seitz, K. H. Koutnik, M. McKenna, and J. N. Garcia, "The 'work' of being a bilingual: Exploring effects of forced language switching on language production and stress level in a real-world setting," *Applied Psycholinguistics*, vol. 41, no. 3, pp. 701–725, May 2020, doi: 10.1017/S0142716420000259.
- [35] M. L. Lara-Cabrera, M. Betancort, C. A. Muñoz-Rubilar, N. R. Novo, and C. D. Cuevas, "The mediating role of resilience in the relationship between perceived stress and mental health," *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, vol. 18, no. 18, p. 9762, Sep. 2021, doi: 10.3390/ijerph18189762.
- [36] F. N. H. M. Isam, E. F. Shair, A. R. Abdullah, N. Nazmi, and N. M. Saad, "Deep learning-based classification of stress levels during real-world driving tasks," in *2022 IEEE-EMBS Conference on Biomedical Engineering and Sciences (IECBES)*, IEEE, Dec. 2022, pp. 286–291. doi: 10.1109/IECBES54088.2022.10079333.
- [37] D. McKay, C. Minaya, and E. A. Storch, "Conducting exposure and response prevention treatment for contamination fears during COVID-19: The behavioral immune system impact on clinician approaches to treatment," *Journal of Anxiety Disorders*, vol. 74, p. 102270, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.janxdis.2020.102270.
- [38] K. K. Hasan, S. M. Mostofa, R. Othman, and D. Mukherjee, "Blended learning during pandemic through knowledge management: an analytical study," *Journal of Information & Knowledge Management*, vol. 21, no. Supp01, May 2022, doi: 10.1142/S0219649222400068.
- [39] Z. Chen, I. C. C. Chan, F. Mehraliyev, R. Law, and Y. Choi, "Typology of people–process–technology framework in refining smart tourism from the perspective of tourism academic experts," *Tourism Recreation Research*, vol. 49, no. 1, pp. 105–117, 2021, doi: 10.1080/02508281.2021.1969114.
- [40] F. Bakioğlu, O. Korkmaz, and H. Ercan, "Fear of covid-19 and positivity: mediating role of intolerance of uncertainty, depression, anxiety, and stress," *International Journal of Mental Health and Addiction*, vol. 19, no. 6, pp. 2369–2382, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.1007/s11469-020-00331-y.
- [41] S. Asif, A. Muddassar, T. Z. Shahzad, M. Raouf, and T. Pervaiz, "Frequency of depression, anxiety and stress among university students," *Pakistan Journal of Medical Sciences*, vol. 36, no. 5, Jun. 2020, doi: 10.12669/pjms.36.5.1873.
- [42] E. Ramón-Arhués, V. Gea-Caballero, J. M. Granada-López, R. Juárez-Vela, B. Pellicer-García, and I. Antón-Solanas, "The prevalence of depression, anxiety and stress and their associated factors in college students," *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, vol. 17, no. 19, p. 7001, Sep. 2020, doi: 10.3390/ijerph17197001.
- [43] Q. Nada, I. Herdiana, and F. Andriani, "Testing the validity and reliability of the depression anxiety stress scale (dass)-21 instrument for individuals with psychodermatology," *Psikohumaniora: Jurnal Penelitian Psikologi*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 153–168, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.21580/pjpp.v7i2.11802.
- [44] M. Makara-Studzińska, E. Tyburski, M. Załuski, K. Adamczyk, J. Mesterhazy, and A. Mesterhazy, "Confirmatory factor analysis of three versions of the depression anxiety stress scale (DASS-42, DASS-21, and DASS-12) in Polish adults," *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, vol. 12, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2021.770532.
- [45] G. Dash and J. Paul, "CB-SEM vs PLS-SEM methods for research in social sciences and technology forecasting," *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, vol. 173, p. 121092, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.techfore.2021.121092.
- [46] J. F. Hair, J. J. Risher, M. Sarstedt, and C. M. Ringle, "When to use and how to report the results of PLS-SEM," *European Business Review*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 2–24, Jan. 2019, doi: 10.1108/EBR-11-2018-0203.

- [47] A. Soberón and W. Stute, "Assessing skewness, kurtosis and normality in linear mixed models," *Journal of Multivariate Analysis*, vol. 161, pp. 123–140, Sep. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.jmva.2017.07.010.
- [48] H. Panduwiyasa, Y. Y. Febrian, M. Saputra, and Z. F. Azzahra, "Performance evaluation of ERP based to ISO/IEC 25010:2011 quality model (a case study)," in *international conference on industrial, enterprise, and system engineering: Collaboration of Science, Technology, and Innovation Toward Sustainable Development*, 2023, p. 020001. doi: 10.1063/5.0174711.
- [49] Z. Mahmud, N. Z.-I. Ismail, N. L. A. Kassim, and M. S. Zainol, "The effects of attitudes towards statistics, perceived ability, learning practices and teaching practices on students' performance in statistics: a review," *Al-Shajarah: Journal of the International Institute of Islamic Thought and Civilization (ISTAC)*, pp. 71–98, 2018.
- [50] J. N. Rouder, C. R. Engelhardt, S. McCabe, and R. D. Morey, "Model comparison in ANOVA," *Psychonomic Bulletin & Review*, vol. 23, no. 6, pp. 1779–1786, Dec. 2016, doi: 10.3758/s13423-016-1026-5.
- [51] A. M. Pérez *et al.*, "Multivariate statistical analysis of the work stress phenomenon in schoolteachers during the current pandemic context in Chile," *Retos*, vol. 49, pp. 1011–1017, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.47197/retos.v49.98898.
- [52] M. Margaretha and A. Wicaksana, "The relationship between person organization fit toward organizational commitment and organizational citizenship behavior: experiences from student activity organization members," *International Journal Of Management Science And Business Administration*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 43–49, 2020, doi: 10.18775/ijmsba.1849-5664-5419.2014.63.1004.
- [53] K. Jochmans, "Heteroscedasticity-robust inference in linear regression models with many covariates," *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, vol. 117, no. 538, pp. 887–896, Apr. 2022, doi: 10.1080/01621459.2020.1831924.
- [54] J. Y.-L. Chan *et al.*, "Mitigating the multicollinearity problem and its machine learning approach: a review," *Mathematics*, vol. 10, no. 8, p. 1283, Apr. 2022, doi: 10.3390/math10081283.
- [55] P. Turner, "Critical values for the Durbin-Watson test in large samples," *Applied Economics Letters*, vol. 27, no. 18, pp. 1495–1499, Oct. 2020, doi: 10.1080/13504851.2019.1691711.
- [56] J. R. Crawford and J. D. Henry, "The depression anxiety stress scales (DASS): normative data and latent structure in a large non-clinical sample," *British Journal of Clinical Psychology*, vol. 42, no. 2, pp. 111–131, Jun. 2003, doi: 10.1348/014466503321903544.
- [57] R. Widiana, Sumiharso, and R. M. Safitri, "Psychometric properties of internet-administered version of depression, anxiety and stress scales (dass-42) in sample Indonesian adult," *Talent Development & Excellence*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 1422–1434, 2020.
- [58] T.-L. Hsia, A.-J. Chiang, J.-H. Wu, N. N. H. Teng, and A. D. Rubin, "What drives e-health usage? integrated institutional forces and top management perspectives," *Computers in Human Behavior*, vol. 97, pp. 260–270, Aug. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.chb.2019.01.010.
- [59] R. A. Manalo, B. de Castro, and C. Uy, "The mediating role of job satisfaction on the effect of motivation to organizational commitment and work engagement of private secondary high school teachers in Metro-Manila," *Review of Integrative Business and Economics Research*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 133–159, 2024AD.

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